

Bridging Physical and Digital Interventions for Active Mobility: Synthesizing Theories and Methods

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Promoting sustainable mobility, particularly cycling, is crucial for combating climate change [2] and enhancing overall well-being [3]. Various strategies can influence human mobility, including *hard* measures such as infrastructure design [1] and *soft* measures such as persuasive digital tools [7] that subtly nudge travel behavior by leveraging human heuristics [6]. However, accurately anticipating how users perceive physical environments or respond to digital nudges remains challenging. Empirical studies highlight a cognitive mismatch between the physical environment as designed by planners and how it is perceived by users [10]. Similarly, for digital nudges to be effective, they need to resonate with these perceptions [8].

This dissertation, with a focus on cycling, aims to improve our understanding of how perception affects travel decisions in interventions that encourage cycling and to reduce the mismatch between perceived and objective environments. It presents three examples of integrating behavioral interventions in sustainable mobility, both theoretically and methodologically, across three Work Packages (WPs): (i) proposing a Spatial Nudging framework to comprehensively map nudging strategies in the mobility domain, (ii) conducting a user study to enhance our understanding of human heuristics in the cycling experience, particularly focusing on the effects of route sequence, and (iii) developing graph-based methods to better align perceived and objective environments along a cycling route. Next, we introduce each WP in detail.

WP 1 focuses on conceptualizing existing nudging strategies within the mobility domain by integrating behavioral theories such as Nudge Theory [9] and the Theory of Affordances [4]. We develop a Spatial Nudging framework that categorizes nudges across various dimensions, providing a comprehensive theoretical link between physical and digital interventions and examining the role of perceived spatial affordances in the efficacy of nudging strategies. The results will lay the groundwork for holistically integrating individual interventions to promote cycling. **WP 2** investigates whether the evaluation of route properties varies based on their sequence at the origin, mid-route, and destination. This work package involves a user study to assess how the composition of these properties influences perceptions of the route. The study employs video recordings of street segments with different characteristics identified as key factors in cycling [5]. We hypothesize that these variations will affect decision-making in route selection. **WP 3** proposes a graph-based method to align physical and digital interventions with users' cognitive expectations, which is critical in route choice tasks. We will use trajectory data mining and spatial knowledge modeling techniques, such as cognitive graphs, to generate realistic cycling trajectories. These graphs, which embed local metric information in their nodes and edges [11], will be used to more accurately capture both the perceived and objective route environments during route planning tasks.

This dissertation fosters a more holistic approach to supporting sustainable travel behavior by linking aspects of physical and digital interventions through behavioral theories in the mobility domain. It provides a valuable resource for designing comprehensive interventions. For research, the thesis advances our understanding of the cognitive processes intrinsic to

cycling. For industry, the proposed graph-matching method offers an innovative path for enhancing route recommendation systems.

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